

Strengthening the Dutch LSH FAIR data stewardship landscape - Installing a national cohort of FAIR LSH fellows

Opportunity to put forward a FAIR LSH fellow from your institute!

NWO provides funding for 10 years to the Thematic Digital Competence Center for Life Sciences & Health (TDCC-LSH) to strengthen and harmonise the digital practices in the life sciences and health domains. One of the projects that is being financed is the **FAIR LSH fellowship programme**.

Summary of the FAIR LSH Fellowship project and the offer to the Dutch universities and UMCs

In 2025, a national cohort of FAIR LSH fellows will be installed that will contribute to tackling prioritized challenges identified by the LSH community in the period 2021-2022, which are described in the TDCC-LSH roadmap¹. The main objectives of the FAIR LSH fellowship programme are:

1. **Enhancing digital competencies across Dutch Health & Life sciences** by skill building in FAIR data stewardship in the RPOs² in the Netherlands
2. **Collaboratively develop solutions and resources related to FAIR implementation** in the LSH domain in the Netherlands
3. **Increase cross-domain collaboration in FAIR implementation** in the LSH domain by expanding and strengthening the network of FAIR LSH experts

FAIR LSH Fellows will be engaged from Dutch UMCs and universities, to learn from each other (peer learning) and from FAIR experts (coaches). **Each university and UMC will be invited to put forward a LSH fellow to take place in the cohort of FAIR LSH fellows**. Through the project, the institutes will get a financial compensation for 0.2 fte for the period of 1 year, enabling them to free up the intended fellow to work in the fellowship programme. The fellows will be guided by a team of coaches and supported by dedicated training & capacity building activities.

The activities of the FAIR LSH fellows will benefit both their own work at their local institutions and contribute to nationally relevant themes. They bring in their own use case and will work collaboratively on resources and guidelines for the LSH domain, thus increasing the joint capacity available to work on solutions to the challenges identified in the TDCC-LSH roadmap. In addition, the individual fellows will gain specific expertise, which is relevant for their own personal development as well as for their department or organisation. They will actively disseminate this knowledge during and after the fellowship period.

LSH FAIR Fellow Profile

The FAIR LSH fellowship is targeted at **individuals with a data stewardship role**. It is important to note that this does not necessarily mean that the fellows have “data steward” as their job title, since there

¹ <https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/media-files/Roadmap%20TDCC%20LSH.pdf>

² RPO: Research Performing Organisation (i.e. university or university medical centre)

are many other experts who are (partly) working in a data stewardship role. Main elements in the profile for the fellows are:

- fellows are affiliated with a research-performing organisation in the Netherlands (RPO, i.e. University or university medical centre)
- fellows have expertise in Life Science and Health domain-specific research in an active/operational role, which is crucial to secure the practical usability of the outputs of their activities in the fellowship
- fellows work actively in data management, and are willing to (further) develop FAIR data management skills, and collaborate in a national network of FAIR fellows
- fellows will bring in and work on their own use cases (which will map to one or more of the prioritized challenges identified in the TDCC-LSH roadmap)
- fellows will contribute to activities on a national level that fit in one or more of the prioritized challenges identified in the TDCC-LSH roadmap
- fellows will commit to disseminating and implementing the outputs (knowledge, expertise, resources (e.g. training materials or implementation guidelines)) further inside and outside their own organisation during and after their fellowship
- the employer/organisation commits to the fellow having allocated time to work on the fellowship projects as well as being able to follow training organized for the fellows and to contribute to the dissemination of the results

Coaches and experts

The fellows will be guided by a team of coaches, who are all experts in their own (sub)domain of LSH and have an extensive track record in data generation, FAIRification, analysis and/or general data handling. The current areas of expertise covered by the coaches' teams are biodiversity, microbial data, bioimaging, genomics, rare diseases, medical informatics and plant phenotyping. All coaches are leading experts in their own field and many of them are part of national infrastructures in the LSH domain like ARISE, UNLOCK, Health-RI, NL-bioimaging, NEMI, X-omics, and NPEC.

Training programme

A training programme will be organised for the duration of the fellowship. The programme consists of a combination of general training sessions relevant for all fellows and tailor-made sessions to help (subgroups of) fellows achieve their goals. It will be complementary to existing training and fellows will receive a certificate.

Project details

- Project start: April 1, 2025
- Start of LSH FAIR Fellows: 1 December 2025 (duration 1 year).
- Kick-off meeting: 27 November 2025, at Health-RI, Utrecht
- Project coordinator: Carla Strubbia (Health-RI, carla.strubbia@health-ri.nl)
- Training & Capacity Building Coordinator: Fieke Schoots (Health-RI, fieke.schoots@health-ri.nl)
- WP leads: Ronald Cornet (AUMC); Sharif Islam (Naturalis)
- Coaches/experts: Wageningen University: Jasper Koehorst, Peter Schaap, Sven Warris; Leiden University: Erik Schultes; Naturalis: Sharif Islam; UMC Groningen: Joeri van der Velde; Groningen University: Ben Giepmans, Pascal de Boer; Amsterdam UMC: Ronald Cornet, Katy Wolstencroft

More information about TDCC-LSH

- TDCC-LSH website: <https://tdcc.nl/about-tdcc/lsh/>
- van Gelder, C. W. G., Zwiers, K., Schoots, F., & Kok, R. (2024). Strengthening the Dutch data driven health & life sciences field: TDCC-LSH facts and figures September 2022- August 2024. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14292810>